

A Study of Presence of Accessory Foramina Transversaria in Dry Human Cervical Vertebrae**Satish Kumar Harioudh¹, Krishna Gopal Tailor², Manjunath V. Motagi³, Swapnil Kumar L Sarda⁴, Prisha Rishi⁵**¹Post Graduate Resident, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore²Associate Professor, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore³Professor & HOD, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore⁴Professor & HOD, LNCT Medical College & Sewakunj Hospital, Indore⁵Assistant Professor, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore

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Abstract:

Introduction: Unique feature of cervical vertebra is the presence of foramen transversaria, which is present in the transverse process of the vertebra and transmits vertebral vessels and autonomic nerves. However sometimes there may be presence of accessory foramen usually seen behind the foramen transversaria known as accessory foramen transversaria (AFT). The present study was aimed to find out the incidence of (AFT) and to study the morphometry of Accessory Foramina Transversaria in dry human cervical vertebrae.

Methodology: 200 dry human cervical vertebrae available in the department of Anatomy, Sri Aurobindo medical college Indore, were observed macroscopically for the presence of accessory foramen transversarium and morphometric study was carried out by using digital vernier calipers.

Results: Out of 200 cervical vertebrae, accessory foramen transversarium was found in 24 cervical vertebrae. Among 24 cervical vertebrae, 21 were typical cervical vertebrae and 3 were atypical cervical vertebrae. In atypical cervical vertebrae, we found accessory foramina transversaria only in C7 and not in C1 and C2.

Conclusion: Unilateral AFT was more common than bilateral as well as oval shaped AFT was found to be more common than round. The knowledge of incidence, shape and size of AFT is clinically important for neurosurgeons, radiologists, anthropologists and anatomists.

Keywords: Vertebral Artery, Foramen Transversaria, Typical And Atypical Cervical Vertebrae.

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Introduction

The identification feature of cervical vertebrae is the presence of foramina transversaria (FT) in the transverse processes of all the cervical vertebrae [1]. In cervical vertebrae, the transverse processes are directed laterally and somewhat forward. Each process presents anterior root and posterior roots ending in anterior and posterior tubercles joined by costo-transverse bar on the lateral side of the foramen transversarium.

The costal element is represented by anterior root, anterior tubercle, costo-transverse bar, posterior tubercle and distal part of the posterior root. The true transverse element is represented by proximal part of the posterior root. The unique development of the cervical transverse processes results in the foramen transversarium. It is created by the genuine transverse process of the vertebra and the vestigial costal element united to the body. The vertebral vessels and nervous plexus are caught

between these two bony parts [2]. The foramen transversarium of all the cervical vertebrae normally transmits the vertebral artery and vein and a branch from cervico-thoracic ganglion (Vertebral nerve) Except C7 in which only vertebral vein passes [1,3]. The foramina transversaria are known to exhibit variations in their shape, size and in number. Sometimes there may be multiple FT or they may be absent. Etiology of such variations may be related to variations in the course of vertebral artery or may be related to development [4].

Sometimes we may find another smaller foramen on the transverse process of cervical vertebrae posterior to the FT, known as An Accessory transverse foramen (AFT) [5]. The course of the vertebral artery may be altered under such circumstances due to variations in shape and size of FT and as well due to the presence of AFT [3]. The

variations in number, shape and size of foramina transversaria of cervical spine may be one of the causes for complaints like headache, migraine, and fainting attacks due to the compression of vertebral artery during neck movements [6].

Knowledge of such anatomical variations of cervical spine especially FT and AFT is essential while performing the complex surgical procedures that involve the screw fixation. It is identified that such osseous and vascular variations of cervical spine increase the risk of damage to vertebral artery during surgical procedures [2]. The knowledge of anatomical variations of foramen transversarium are important for the clinicians, neurologists, neurosurgeons, radiologists for interpreting X ray and CT scans [4].

There are enough studies and case reports regarding variations in the origin and course of vertebral artery. However, fewer studies are available on the morphometry of AFT as compared to the incidence of the accessory transverse foramina. So, the present study was done with the aim to find out the incidence of accessory foramina transversaria (AFT) along with morphometry of AFT in dry human cervical vertebra.

Material and Methodology

This study was performed on 200 adult dry cervical vertebrae including typical and atypical of unknown age and sex available in the Department of Anatomy, SAIMS and PGI, Indore.

All the vertebrae were segregated into Typical and Atypical and labelled accordingly. Then all the typical and atypical Vertebrae were observed for the presence of accessory foramen transversarium (AFT). Photographs of vertebrae having AFT unilaterally or bilaterally were taken. Shapes of the AFT were noted Followed by measurements of maximum AP Diameter and Transverse Diameter

of AFT. All measurements were taken by using Digital Vernier Callipers.

Study Design: Analytical Cross sectional

Inclusion Criteria: Cervical vertebrae available in the Department of Anatomy, SAIMS and PGI, Indore.

Exclusion criteria: Damaged and pathologically abnormal bones was excluded from the study

Statistical Analysis:

- The data was collected and entered in MS excel 2010. Then Data was analyzed and presented in frequency table.
- Descriptive statistics is calculated as mean and SD for quantitative variable and frequency and percentage for qualitative or categorical variables. Pie or bar diagram is used for Qualitative or demographical variables. Z test is applied for comparison between two proportions.
- p value <0.05 is considered as statistically significant result and p value >0.05 is considered as statistically insignificant result

Observations and Results

Out of 200 cervical vertebrae, 24 vertebrae (12%) were having presence of accessory foramina transversaria. Among 24 vertebrae, 21 were typical cervical vertebrae and 3 were atypical cervical vertebrae. In atypical cervical vertebrae, we found accessory foramina transversaria only in C7 and not in C1 and C2. Out of 24 vertebrae, unilateral accessory foramen transversarium was found in 14 (7%) vertebrae and bilateral accessory foramen transversarium was found in 10 (5%) vertebrae. Thus, unilateral accessory foramen transversarium was more common than bilateral. The Incidence of both Unilateral and Bilateral AFT in these vertebrae is shown in Table No.1.

Table 1: Incidence of AFT in dry human cervical vertebrae

Cervical vertebrae	Total Number(200)	Presence of AFT (N)	Incidence of AFT
Total	200	24	12%
Typical	121	21	10.5%
Atypical	79	3	1.5%

Figure 1: Unilateral AFT in typical cervical vertebra

Figure 2: Bilateral AFT in typical cervical vertebra

Figure 3: Unilateral AFT in C7 cervical vertebra

Shape of the cervical vertebrae: Proportion of accessory foramina transversaria according to its shape is shown in Table no.2.

Table 2: Proportion of Accessory Foramina transversaria according to its Shape

Type of Vertebrae	Presence of AFT (N)	Shape	Total	Proportion
Typical	21	Round	14	66.6%
		Oval	16	76.19%
Atypical	3	Round	2	66.6%
		Oval	2	66.6%

Out of 21 typical cervical vertebrae, Oval shaped AFT (76.19%) was more common than the round shape (66.6%).

However, in atypical cervical vertebrae, both round and oval shapes of AFT was seen in equal proportion (66.6%).

Maximum AP and Transverse Diameter of AFT: As shown in Table no.3, Mean Anteroposterior Diameter of AFT on right side was 2.4 ± 0.598 and on left side was 2.46 ± 0.639 , mean transverse diameter of AFT on right side was 1.8 ± 0.615 and on left side was 1.93 ± 0.593 .

Table 3: Comparison of Means of maximum Anteroposterior (AP) diameter and maximum Transverse Diameter (TD) of AFT on right and Left sides

Diameter	Side	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T test	DF	P-value
APD	Right	20	2.4000	0.59824	0.317	33	0.753
	Left	15	2.4667	0.63994			
TD	Right	20	1.8000	0.61559	0.644	33	0.524
	Left	15	1.9333	0.59362			

Comparison of means of AP and Transverse diameters showed no significant difference on both the sides (p value 0.753 for AP diameter) and (p value 0.524 for TD).

Discussion

Embryologically, vertebrae form from the sclerotome portions of the somites, which are derived from paraxial mesoderm. Similarly vertebral arteries are formed from cervical intersegmental arteries which arise from the dorsolateral aspect of the dorsal aorta. These arteries join with one another and form the longitudinal anastomotic channels, except the

seventh cervical intersegmental artery. Remaining arteries regress and modifies to form the vertebral artery [2]. When there is failure in controlled regression it leads to variations in the origin and course of vertebral artery as it passes through FT, therefore variations in vertebral artery might lead to variations in foramen and vice versa [8].

AFT may be unilateral or bilateral. The present study showed AFT was more common in typical cervical vertebrae as compared to atypical.

In the table 4, the incidence of the AFT of present study was compared with various other studies.

Table 4: Comparison of incidence of AFT with other studies

Authors	No of cervical vertebrae	Incidence of AFT	Unilateral AFT	Bilateral AFT
Das et al [3]	132	1.5%	-	-
Taitz et al [8]	480	7%	-	-
Ranjan R et al. [9]	170	14.12%	11.76%	2.35%
Murlimanju et al [10]	363	1.60%	1.40%	0.30%
Shital et al. [11]	210	16.19%	9.52%	6.67%
Gujar et al. [12]	150	27.33%	18%	9.33%
Akhtar et al [13]	174	14.36%	11.49%	2.87%
Chaudhari et al. [14]	133	23.15%	14.73%	8.42%
Manoj P et al. [15]	163	14.72%	4.90%	9.81%
Sharma et al. [16]	200	8%	3.50%	4.50%
Patra et al. [17]	150	22%	10.67%	11.33%
Thimmaraju sumalatha et al. [18]	148	11.48%	5.40%	6.08%
Katikireddi R S et al. [19]	100	3	2	1
Manjunanth M et al. 2018 [20]	100	20%	12%	08%
Present study 2024	200	12%	7%	5%

From various studies it was observed that incidence of AFT varies from 1.5% to 27.33%. Das et al. [3] in their study found double foramina transversaria

unilaterally and bilaterally only in two different cervical vertebrae. Similarly, Taitz et al. [8] in their study on 480 cervical vertebrae observed the

doubling of foramina transversaria in 34 cases and also found triple foramina transversaria in one vertebrae and absence of foramen in 4 cases. In the present study we observed 24 vertebrae showed AFT out of 200 and we have not found more than one accessory foramen. In the present study we also observed the incidence of AFT is more in typical cervical vertebrae as compared to atypical. Unilateral AFT was more common than bilateral in our study. This is in line with studies done by Ranjan R et al. [9], Muralimanju et al. [8], Shital et al. [11], Gujar et al. [12], Akhtar et al. [13], Choudhari et al [14]. In contrast to this bilateral AFT was reported more by Manoj P et al. [15], sharma et al. [16], Patra et al. [17], Thimmaraju Sumalatha et al. [18]. Oval shaped AFT was more commonly observed in our study followed by round shape in contrast study done by Kaur S et al. [2] classified AFT as Complete and incomplete in typical cervical vertebrae.

In the present study in all cervical vertebrae, Mean Anteroposterior Diameter of AFT on right side was 2.4 ± 0.598 and on left side was 2.46 ± 0.639 , mean transverse diameter of AFT on right side was 1.8 ± 0.615 and on left side was 1.93 ± 0.593 . In contrast, the study done by Ranjan R et al. [9], reported diameters of AFT (AP and Transverse) on right and left side in individual cervical vertebra.

The Knowledge of Presence of AFT and its morphological variations is clinically important as the course of the vertebral artery may be altered as per the variant state of foramen transversaria. Even the presence of extra foramina in the transverse processes may indicate multiplication of the neurovascular structures running through them. So, the knowledge and understanding of such anatomical variations is very much relevant for clinicians, surgeons and radiologists.

Conclusion

Incidence of AFT was more common in typical cervical vertebrae as compared to atypical vertebrae. Unilateral AFT in cervical vertebrae was more common than Bilateral. In atypical cervical vertebrae, only C7 cervical vertebrae showed AFT. Oval shaped AFT was more commonly found than the round shape. Maximum AP and Transverse diameter of AFT showed no significant difference. The following anatomical variations highlight the importance of preoperative radiological tests to rule out any of these variations for achieving better surgical outcomes in this region.

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